

ATOMIC ABSORPTION SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN SELECTED NIGERIAN FOODS

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ABSTRACT

The levels of copper content was determined in selected food samples of cereals, meat and fish, egg, vegetables, fruits and nuts, seeds and legumes, tubers and roots and other groups obtained in Akure, Nigeria by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. Copper concentration significantly varied among studied foods cereal groups accumulated the highest values (0.34 to 0.81mg100g⁻¹), while the lowest concentrations were recorded from vegetables (0.12 to 0.36mg100g⁻¹). The results indicated that the copper contents of these food samples were comparable with average values of foods from other countries. Copper deficiency in Nigerians is rare because copper is widely distributed in foods eaten by the populace

KEYWORDS: Copper, Nigerian foods, food groups, deficiency, dietary intake

INTRODUCTION

Food is one of the basic necessities of human life. It is necessary for growth, body building, strong teeth, prevention of diseases, part of enzymes needed in the body, manufacture hemoglobin, the integrity of connective tissue, bones, nerves, the cardiovascular system, the immune system and the blood clotting system are all in part dependent on food.

More than one-third of the dietary nutrients one needs to maintain life are minerals. They play very important roles in the human and animal bodies and are also related to such diseases as cancer and high blood pressure. It is important to make sure that the diets contain sufficient amounts of each (Nieman *et al* 1992). The bioavailability of trace minerals is an issue in planning diets. Even if a food is high in a particular mineral, it may not supply much to the body unless the mineral is absorbed well in the small intestine (Wardlaw 1999). Many factors found in foods inhibit mineral absorption. In general, animal sources of minerals are superior to plant sources because they show more efficient absorption. Animal sources also often contain factors that enhance mineral absorption, even for those trace minerals supplied by plant foods in a meal (Chandra 1997).

Copper one of the trace elements, is a part of contain enzymes (Anhwange *et al* 2005). It aids in iron metabolism and contributes to the activity of other enzymes. About 55 – 75% of dietary copper is absorbed, with higher intakes associated with lower absorption. Phytate, certain amino acids, vitamin C, dietary fiber, zinc and iron may all interfere with copper absorption (Lonnerdal 1996) foods naturally contains copper. One eats and drink about 1 milligram (1/1000 of a gram) of copper everyday. Copper is necessary in ones diet for good health (Habeck 2005). Copper deficiency due to inadequate dietary intake is rare (Food Data Charts 2007).

The aims of the present study were to provide knowledge of essential copper concentration in some selected Nigerian. Akure land is considered unpolluted area far from the large industrial center in Nigeria and it is situated in southwest corner of the country.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The food samples (Table 1) were obtained on Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria in July 2006. They were cleaned to remove dirt, washed in deionised water, oven dried at 60°C for 2 –4h depending on sample, ground in

Table 1: Common names, Local names and Botanical names of samples analyzed.

Common Names	Local Names	Botanical Names.
Cereals		
Indomine noddles	-	-
Maize	Agbado	<i>Zea mays</i>
Pap	Ogi	<i>Zea mays</i>
Rice	Iresi	<i>Oryza sativa</i>
Sorghum	Oka baba	<i>Sorghum vulgare</i>
Meat and Fish		
Meat flesh	Eran	-
Liver	Edo	-
Fish	Eja	<i>Tilapia nicoticus</i>
Grayfish	Ede pupa	<i>Procambaris clarkii</i>
Egg products		
Egg	Eyin	-
Vegetables		
Onion	Alubosa	<i>Allium cepa</i>
Pepper	Ata rodo	<i>Capsicum annum</i>
Garden egg	Igba	<i>Solanum melongena</i>
Tomatoes	Tomati	<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>
Spinach	Tete	<i>Amaranthus spp</i>
Fruits and Nuts		
Kolanut	Obi	<i>Cola nitida</i>
Okra	Ila	<i>Hibiscus esculentum</i>
Ginger	-	<i>Zingiber officinal</i>
Carrot	-	<i>Carrota</i>
Walnut	Awusa	<i>Juglанда ceae</i>
Pineapple	Ope oyinbo	<i>Ananas comosa</i>
Guava	-	<i>Psidium guajava</i>
Coconut	Agbon	<i>Coco nucifera</i>
Seeds and legumes		
Cowpea (red)	Ewa pupa	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>
Groundnut	Epa	<i>Arachis Hypogea</i>
Locust bean	Iru	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>
Groundnut cake	Kulikuli	<i>Arachis hypogea</i>
Soya been	-	<i>Glycine max</i>
Melon	Egunsi	<i>Seamon indicum</i>

Kenwood blender, sieved with a mesh of aperture 425Nm and stored prior to analysis. Each sample (0.5g) was dry ashed in a muffle furnace with temperature of 550°C for 2-4h (depending on the sample). The ashed sample was dissolved in little quantity of 2m HCl, Filtered and made up to 50cm³ using 2M HCl. The selenium content was determined using Pye Unicam atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Determinations were in triplicate. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS for windows 10.0.

Table 2: copper content (mg100g⁻¹DM) of selected foods analyzed

Samples	Mean ± Std. error
Cereals	
Indomine noddle	0.81±0.1
Maize	0.34±0.1
Pap	0.65±0.2
Rice	0.47±0.1
Sorghum	0.48±0.3
Meat and fish	
Meat	0.48±0.2
Liver	0.19±0.2
Fish	0.44±0.1
Crayfish	0.47±0.3
Egg products	
Egg	0.69±0.1
Vegetables	
Onion	0.36±0.2
Pepper	0.31±0.2
Garden egg	0.12±0.1
Tomatoes	0.15±0.2
Spinach	0.33±0.1
Fruits and Nuts	
Kolanut	0.38±0.3
Okra	0.27±0.3
Ginger	0.15±0.3
Carrot	0.25±0.3
Walnut	0.28±0.3
Pineapple	0.27±0.2
Guava	0.22±0.2
Coconut	0.46±0.2
Seeds and legumes	
Cowpea	0.19±0.5
Groundnut	0.48±0.5
Locust been	0.32±0.5
Groundnut cake	0.25±0.5
Soya been	0.19±0.5
Melon	0.29±0.5
Tuber and Roots	
Cassava flour (gari)	0.35±0.2
Banana	0.32±0.3
Cocoyam	0.25±0.1
Potatoes	0.29±0.3
Plantain	0.34±0.3
Yam (Yellow)	0.18±0.2
Yam (bitter)	0.36±0.3
Yam flour (white)	0.38±0.3
Others	
Biscuit	0.17±0.2
Bread	0.57±0.2
Salt	0.72±0.2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean copper contents of each food group are shown in Table 1. Cereals produced values ranging from 0.34 (maize) to 0.81mg100g⁻¹ (indomine noddles). In meat and fish group the values ranged between 0.19 (liver) to 0.48mg100g⁻¹ (meat flash). Vegetables values were 0.12 (garden egg) to 0.36mg100g⁻¹ (Onion). Fruits and nuts, seeds and legumes, tubers and roots and other groups produced mean (mg100g⁻¹) values as follows: 0.15 to 0.46, 0.19 to 0.48, 0.18 to 0.38 and 0.17 to 0.72 respectively. Foods with the highest nutrient density for copper were cereals, fish, crayfish, legumes, nuts, fruits and eggs. These foods may be termed as good sources of copper.

The copper data obtained for food samples in this study were roughly similar to those reported food samples elsewhere. Nieman *et al* (1992) reported values of 0.32 to 0.98mg/l; Wardlaw (1999) reported 0.2 to 2.0mg100g⁻¹ for seeds, wheat germ, nuts, yeast, liver, lobster and oysters Aremu *et al* (2006) reported between 0.4 to 1.9mg100g⁻¹ for seeds and legumes and in Food Data Chart (2007), Tr- 1.1mg/100g-1 recorded for biscuits, cereals, cake, deserts (ND-5.mg100 g⁻¹); Egg and cheese dishes (0.03 to 0.1mg100g⁻¹); fast and oils (ND – 0.02mg100g⁻¹) fish and other sea foods (ND – 7.6mg100g⁻¹), fruit (ND – 6.0mg100g⁻¹); meats and meat products (ND –9.9mg100g⁻¹)milk and milk products (ND – 0.5mg100g⁻¹), nuts (ND – 1.1mg100g⁻¹); sauces and condiments (ND – 1.1mg100g⁻¹); soups (0.02 – 0.1mg100g⁻¹) sugars, jams and spreads (ND – 0.7mg100g⁻¹); sweets (ND – 0.4mg100g⁻¹) and vegetables (ND – 0.8mg100⁻¹).

The values reported by other authors were higher than our data. Korenekova *et al* (2002) reported 4.43 to 70.37mgkg⁻¹ for cattle in Slovak Republic, Falandysz *et al* (2005) reported 1.9 to 8.3mgkg⁻¹ for kidney, liver, muscle tissues of red deer from Warania and Mazury, Poland, while Hossain and Khan (2001) reported 12.2 – 75.6mgkg⁻¹ for shrimp and lobster from the Bay of Bengal and 23.4 to 62.1mgkg⁻¹ for vegetables (Al-Khateeb and Leilah 2005).

Significant differences in the food analyzed and those from other countries may be due to soil conditions. Wardlaw (1999) noted that soil conditions greatly affect the copper content of plants foods. In addition, water may supply 13 – 50% of copper needs depending on the copper content of the local soil (Olivares and Ricardo, 1996).

Copper has an estimated safe and adequate daily dietary intake of 1.5 to 3mgday⁻¹ for adults. Human average intake is about 0.6 to 1.6mgdaily. Women generally have the lower in takes. Copper is part of several important enzymes that are needed for proper utilization of iron and for the manufacture of hemoglobin and red blood cells in the bone marrow. The integrity of connective tissue, bones nerves, the cardiovascular system, the immune system, and the blood clotting system are all in part dependent on copper (Turnlland 1988). The liver, kidney, hair and brain contain the highest concentrations of copper (Shils *et al* 1999).

Copper deficiency can result from the use of antacids by binding copper in the intestines and overzealous supplementation of zinc can hamper copper absorption. Zinc increases synthesis of the protein metallothionein, which binds both minerals (Wardlaw 1999). In animals, zinc supplements can decrease copper absorption, leading to anemia and heart disease. Because copper is widely is very rare (Nieman *et al.*, 1992).

Dietary copper is not toxic to humans because intakes are usually low and because the bodies can regulate copper storage through balladry excretion (Reddy and love, 1999). An inherited disease called Wilson's disease results in accumulation of copper in the lower, brain, kidneys and cornea of the eye. The biochemical defect that causes Wilson's disease is present at birth, but usually is not detected until later childhood, adolescence, or young adulthood. Lifelong treatment of this disease is taking of agents that bind copper such as penicillamine. Wilson's disease causes tissue damage and reduces the mental degeneration.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained showed that the selected foods contained substantial amount of copper. Then the study conducted that they are valuable sources of this mineral nutrient which would be beneficial to the health of human and animals. It is recommended that, complementary mixtures of these foods should be taken to ensure adequate dietary intake.

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